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RESEARCH OF IRRIGATED SOILS AND THEIR PROPERTIES IN BUKHARA DISTRICT

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Annotation. The main part of 4304.32 thousand hectares of irrigated land of our republic (about 50%) consists of soils with varying degrees of salinity, which reduces the overall productivity of agricultural crops in irrigated areas. This article provides detailed information about the irrigated soils of Bukhara district and their agrophysical properties. In addition, measures to improve soil fertility were presented.

Key words: Bukhara district, irrigated soils, soil mechanical composition, Zarafshan river delta, reclamation, soil fertility, irrigation standards, salinity, parent rock, alluvial, loess sands, groundwater, mineralization

Introduction. Bukhara region is located in the lower reaches of the Zarafshan River. The entire oasis consists of areas formed by wide and short river beds. In the wide part of the river, in the lower part of Bukhara, there are oases of Kara Kul.[3.4.]

The reason for the deterioration of the ecological and melioration situation in the irrigated dekhkan region is the result of the extensive use of existing water and land resources. In all projects for the development of new lands, it was planned to discharge water from collector-drainage networks into lowlands and riverbeds.

As a result of the large-scale implementation of projects that are not theoretically and practically justified, the quality of river waters deteriorates sharply, artificial lakes and swamps are formed around the developed areas, the natural balance is disturbed, and the ecological situation worsens.

The most negative aspect of salinization is that it destroys the soil structure, worsens the water-physical, physico-chemical properties, affects the microbiological activity and other properties of soils, causing soil degradation.

To prevent salinization and secondary salinization and successfully solve the problems of land reclamation, it is necessary to carry out "Mapping of Saline Soils" on arable lands.

This requires examining the territories, carefully studying the degree of salinity of the soil cover and soil subsoil, and types of salinity.

Research object and method. According to the climatic conditions of the Bukhara district, the semi-desert zone belongs to the continental subtropical climate group. The climate of the district is sharply continental and extremely dry. This region is characterized by the alternation of tropical and temperate air masses by season, the intensification of transpiration processes in the warm season, and the intensification of the Asian current of the polar front in the cold season. Therefore, Bukhara district has stable dry and hot weather in summer, and extremely unstable cold weather in winter.

The irrigated lands of Bukhara district are mainly developed on Quaternary deposits - loess, alluvial and proluvial rocks.

The thickness of this Quaternary layer is 17-20 m, and sometimes 30 m. The composition of these deposits is made up of gravel, sand, loam and agro-irrigation layers, which are found in each layer and at different depths.

In the upper part of the Zarafshon River delta, stones, gravel and sand are found in Quaternary rocks, while in the middle and lower reaches, sand, then sand, silt and occasionally clay are distributed.

Agroirrigation layers (1-3m) developed on Quaternary alluvial deposits, which were formed under the influence of human activity.

The irrigated lands of the Bukhara district, including F. Alov, O. Ubaydov, developed on Quaternary alluvial deposits located at a depth of 14-20 m in the 5th-6th centuries BC. Nowadays, the upper part of these alluvial deposits is covered with modern, cultural anthropogenic agroirrigation layers. The level and degree of mineralization of groundwater are distributed in these local and alluvial rocks, and under the influence of various micro- and meso-reliefs, they periodically lead to the formation of various salinization processes.[2.]

Soil samples taken from Bukhara districts were chemically analyzed in laboratory conditions, the amount of salts was determined, and the type and degree of salinity in them were determined according to the I and II methods of water absorption (Lebedev).

As a result of field research and laboratory analysis, it was found that the quantitative indicators of salts, the degree of salinity and types of salinity are different in different areas of the district.

The first sources for recording, accounting and compiling cartograms of saline soils are mapping materials based on water absorption analyses and other modern rapid methods for determining the degree of soil salinity (electroconductometric method).

Research results. When leaching, it is necessary to take into account the degree of salinity, mechanical composition, water permeability (water-physical properties) of the soil, and the amount and reserves of salts in the root zone (0-1m). Water standards for leaching vary depending on the mechanical composition. Depending on the mechanical composition of the soil, the average salt leaching rate is 3000-3500 m³/ha for light layered soils, 3500-5000 m³/ha for moderately saline soils by 2-3 times of flooding, 4000-5000 m³/ha for strongly saline soils by 3 times of flooding, 5000-6500 m³/ha for very saline soils of different mechanical composition by 3-4 times of flooding, and 6000-7500 m³/ha for strongly and very strongly saline soils of heavy mechanical composition by 3-4 times of flooding. The amount of salts in the soil after salt leaching should be reduced to 0.01% of chlorine ions and to 0.4-0.6% of dry matter. When determining the standards of salinization, the recommendations of UzPITI (now PSUEMTI) (Scientific Research Institute of Cotton Breeding, Seed Production and Agrotechnology) (Table 1) and available data (based on salinity cartograms according to the formula of A.E. Nerozin) are used.

The hydrogeological conditions of the Bukhara district are extremely complex, and the main sources of groundwater are water seeping from irrigation networks and irrigated fields, as well as groundwater flowing from the Zarafshan River, which occupy a major place in the balance of seepage waters.

Seepage waters are detected at a depth of 1-2 m to 2-3 m. In the lowlands, groundwater is detected at a depth of 1-2 m, even 0.5-1 m, where meadow and swamp-meadow soils are formed.

In the conditions of the natural and artificially drained district, as a result of irrigation at high rates for many years, large amounts of water absorbed by the soil, merge with groundwater, allowing them to rise sharply to the surface, which in turn leads to rapid salt accumulation in the soil and deterioration of the reclamation condition of irrigated lands. The state of groundwater is seasonal, and if the depth typical for these lands decreases to 2-3 meters after the end of the growing season, it increases to 0.5-1.5 meters during the growing season, with an amplitude of seasonal fluctuations of

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1.0-1.5 meters. The fact that in the main part of the district, regardless of the geomorphological region to which they belong, is located much higher than the optimal depth, in turn, actively participates in the processes of soil formation and soil salinization.

Experiments show that with the loosening of the mechanical structure of the soil, both the absorption power and the water column increase, the leaching of salts becomes easier, and vice versa, not only does it become more difficult, but also the saline vegetation that has formed in the depths of the soil due to the capillary rise of saline waters has a negative effect on the root system.[4]

In the course of scientific research, it became clear that the amount of physical clay in the mechanical structure of these soils changes with distance from the canal. If in areas located closer to the canal, the amount of physical clay is 30-32% in a thickness of 0-66 cm, then in areas located at 200 and 300 m, the amount of these fractions increases to 40%. As the amount of medium sand fractions increases in the horizons of the soil cross-section, the formation of heavy sandy soils is observed in the fields with increasing distance from the canal. Based on the collected data, the quantitative and qualitative changes in the mechanical composition of the studied soils, based on the above laws, depend not only on the influence of the parent rock and relief, but also on the degree of turbidity of suspended sediments, the length of irrigation channels, and the composition of particles in the water flowing in the ditches located in the fields. The soils of the Bukhara district are distributed in the steppe soils region.

The soils of the district are mainly irrigated barren grassland, irrigated grassland-steppe, irrigated grassland, irrigated grassland alluvial, and swamp-grassland.

Conclusion. Compared to other soils of the steppe zone, irrigated grassland soils are relatively rich in humus (1.1-1.45%) and nitrogen (0.08-0.12%). The deep penetration of humus into agroirrigation runoff sludge ensures its high reserves in the soil profile. Irrigated grassland soils formed on ancient alluvial and deluvial-proluvial surfaces have a low humus content (0.5-0.7), since their predecessors, gray-brown or barren soils, had a low organic matter content.

These soils contain a small amount of gypsum (0.12-0.25%) and it does not prevent the development of the salinization process. Therefore, salinization occurs due to the penetration of sodium and magnesium ions into the lower part of the root zone, and in some cases into the absorption capacity. Salinity leads to a decrease in the water permeability of the soil. It causes compaction of the soil after irrigation and other negative properties. Carbonation is uniform across the soil section - 8.8-9.3% SO₂. In general, irrigated pasture soils have a fairly high productivity and constitute a valuable part of the land fund of the Bukhara region.

In the current and ancient deltas of Zarafshan, as well as in the areas of its upper and first upper terraces, small massifs between irrigated pasture soils are located marshy-meadow soils, most of which are irrigated soils. These soils are formed in local swamps in conditions where the groundwater level is 0.5-1 m, and a strong salinization process is taking place. Therefore, these soils are subject not only to swamping, but also to salinization. They are mainly found in a weak and moderately saline state.

According to their mechanical composition, the soils are heavy and medium sandy. The amount of humus in the arable layer of swampy-meadow soils is about

3%. These soils are poorly supplied with total phosphorus reserves, as well as potassium. (Soil Cover Atlas of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2010)

In implementing measures aimed at improving the land reclamation condition, the correct selection of reclamation objects that need to be improved is considered extremely important, and an integrated approach to this issue is necessary from a scientific and practical perspective.

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